

from other sources for use on the same occasion. Of course, this was apart from the forest of Palms and other decorative plants in pots. In preparation for supplying unusually large quantities at one time the development of some flowers is retarded in the hot-houses, and that of others is hurried forward.

The loss on unsold flowers is equitably divided pro rata among consignors in the class in which it occurs. Quality is in no small degree determined by weather, soft and mussy stock coming in after muggy days. General high quality of the great masses of flowers seen here is remarkable, as is also their freshness. A much higher grade is demanded now by retail buyers than a half dozen years ago, and flowers sold on the streets are especially of better quality during the past three or four years. The choicest varieties and newest sorts are offered here, and fragrant blossoms are always in special request.

The first buyers come as early as seven o'clock in the morning. Flowers looking dewy and fresh have already been taken from the largest refrigerators used for this sort of storage in the country and displayed in the salesroom, and others continue to arrive. Of carnations, from 5,000 to 25,000 are handled in one day, as many more violets and lily-of-the-valley, and 40,000 roses. At six o'clock in the evening the receiving and selling is over, and the storing of the freshest flowers still unsold concludes the work of the day. It is pleasant to record the fact that any flowers left over are presented to the hospitals.

New York.

M. B. C.

A New Hybrid Oak in the Indian Territory.

WHILE collecting along a little rocky branch a mile south-west of Sapulpa, Indian Territory, on September 20th, I was led to observe more closely the Texas Red Oak, *Quercus Texana*, on account of its occurrence in such large numbers, and while doing this I came upon an Oak plainly different from that species, and which I thought to be a hybrid. After a careful study of it and the surrounding trees, I became satisfied that it was a hybrid between the Black Jack Oak and the Black Oak. It may be briefly described as *Q. Marilandica* × *velutina*, n. hyb.: a tall, slender tree, scarcely resembling either *Q. Marilandica* or *Q. velutina* in general appearance, but more like the latter; trunk and branches exactly like those of *Q. Marilandica*, but twigs and branchlets like those of *Q. velutina*; buds nearly like those of *Q. velutina*, but larger; leaves broader at the upper end and tapering to a narrow, sometimes cordate base, three to five lobed; lobing very various, some like *Q. Marilandica* and some like *Q. velutina*, all shortly bristle-tipped; upper surface of leaves as in *Q. Marilandica*, but lower surface nearly like that in *Q. velutina*, but somewhat rusty-downy; petioles slender, nearly smooth and averaging about one inch in length; acorns long and slender-pointed, very rusty-downy when young, but nearly smooth when mature, striped with alternating lines of black and yellow, as in *Q. Marilandica*; cup top-shaped, with a scaly edge, longer than that of either *Q. Marilandica* or *Q. velutina*, but approaching the latter more nearly. One tree only, sixty feet in height, with a trunk about fifteen inches in diameter, and growing in a rocky hollow where *Q. Texana* is abundant, and *Q. Marilandica*, *Q. minor* and *Q. velutina* are common.

Independence, Mo.

B. F. Bush.

The Names of some North American Tree Willows.

SALIX LONGIFOLIA, Muehlenberg (*Neue Schrift. Gesell Nat. Fr.*, Berlin, iv., 238, t. 6, f. 6), was published in 1803. In 1778 Lamarck had published in his *Fl. Franç.* (ii., 232) a *Salix longifolia* to which he referred the *Salix viminalis* of Linnæus, and the next oldest name of Muehlenberg's plant, *Salix fluviatilis* of Nuttall (*Sylva*, i., 73), published in 1842, must be adopted.

Salix rostrata, Richardson (*Arctic Exped.*, 753), was published in 1823. In 1799 Thuillier had published in the second

edition of his *Flore des Environs de Paris* a *Salix rostrata* now referred to *Salix repens* of Linnæus. Asa Gray in 1867 (*Man.*, ed. 5, 564) called the Beaked Willow *Salix livida*, var. *occidentalis*. The name *occidentalis* had been used for a West Indian species by Koch in 1828, and four other varietal names, *latifolia*, *lanata*, *obovata* and *lanceolata*, given to it by Andersson, had all been previously employed in this genus. This common, familiar and widely distributed tree being, therefore, deprived by the rules established by American botanists of any name at all, I am glad to associate with it that of Mr. S. B. Bebb, of Illinois, the learned, industrious and distinguished salicologist of the United States, to whom, more than to any one else of this generation, we owe our knowledge of American Willows, and to call it *Salix Bebbiana*.

Salix flavescens, Nuttall (*Sylva*, i., 65), was published in 1842. In 1828 Host published in his *Salix* (31, t. 101) a *Salix flavescens* now referred to *Salix Arbuscula*, Linnæus, and this name being thus unavailable for the Rocky Mountain tree, I propose to call it *Salix Nuttallii* in honor of Thomas Nuttall, who discovered and first described it. The variety *Salix flavescens*, var. *capreoides*, Bebb (*GARDEN AND FOREST*, viii., 373), thus becomes *Salix Nuttallii*, var. *capreoides*.

A large-leaved form of *Salix lasiandra* discovered by Dr. David Lyall in 1859 on the lower Fraser River was first described by Andersson (*Sal. Monog.*, 34, f. 23) as *Salix lancifolia*, and in 1868 (De Candolle, *Prodr.*, xvi., pt. ii., 205) as *Salix lucida*, β *macrophylla*. This specific and varietal name having been previously used in *Salix*, I propose for this variety the name of its discoverer, and call it *Salix lasiandra*, var. *Lyallii*.

C. S. S.

Plant Notes.

CRATÆGUS APIIFOLIA.—This is a small tree, with delicate, nearly circular, deeply cleft and divided leaves, of the southern states, where it is mostly confined to the coast region, although west of the Mississippi River it ranges inland to central Arkansas. Plants raised from seed gathered near Little Rock, Arkansas, have produced plants which have proved fairly hardy in the Arnold Arboretum, although they have not flowered there yet. The Parsley Haw, as *Cratægus apiifolia* is often called, is one of the most delicate and beautiful species of the whole genus, and in the Arboretum this autumn it has been specially noticeable for the brilliant deep red color assumed by some of the leaves, while others on the same branch remain unchanged in color. Quite uninjured by frost, the leaves were in their greatest beauty last week.

ROSA SETIGERA.—The beautiful Prairie Rose should receive another word of praise for the colors it takes on late in the autumn, when the long arching stems turn dark purple and are coated with a glaucous bloom, and the leaves are brilliant orange and scarlet. It is one of the most valuable of all shrubs, and many people think the most beautiful Rose. Its merit as an ornamental plant has often been pointed out in these columns, but we venture to remind our readers of its hardiness and vigor, the rapidness of its growth, its graceful habit, and its many clusters of large pure pink flowers, which open later than those of most single-flowered Roses. The Prairie Rose has been largely used with good effect in some of the Boston parks, in which it flowered freely this year, and its beauty was a revelation to the public. This, perhaps, will lead to a more general use of this delightful plant.

LEUCOTHÖE RACEMOSA.—The most brilliant plant we know, however, in the middle of November in the northern states, is *Leucothöe racemosa*, a common shrub in moist thickets in the neighborhood of the Atlantic and Gulf coasts of North America, from Massachusetts southward. This is just now the most conspicuous shrub in the Arnold Arboretum, in Boston, where it has been planted in large numbers, and an object of great beauty, with flaming scarlet leaves which